

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology

Title of the course: ***Clinical Toxicology*** Course number

Level: 4th Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours/week: **Theory 2**

Reference text:

- 1- Casarett and Doull, Toxicology, the Basic Science of Poisons; latest edition.
- 2-Gossel TA, Bricker TD, (Eds.); Principles of Clinical Toxicology; latest edition.
- 3-Viccellio P, (Ed.); Handbook of Medicinal Toxicology; latest edition.

Objectives: To study the principle of exposure to different chemicals and environmental factors, their sources, mechanisms of toxicity and their risk to human being; it enables students to understand the required measures to protect living organisms against the suspected toxic hazards in addition the course aims to provide students with the principles and skills required to deal with the toxicity of chemicals and drugs in clinical settings; it enables students to correlate signs and symptoms of toxicity with the analytical data, and to know how to establish preventive and therapeutic measures for poisoning cases.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction: general consideration; host factor, environmental factors of toxic effects.	3
2	Target organs and systemic toxicology; Respiratory system, Liver, Kidney, Skin, Nervous system, cardiovascular system, Blood.	12
3	Initial Evaluation and Management of the Poisoned Patient. Including pediatric poisoning and special consideration in the geriatric patient	3

4	Drug Toxicity: Over the counter drugs; caffeine; theophylline; antihistamine and decongestant; non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; vitamins.	3
5	Prescription Medications: Cardiovascular drugs; beta blockers; ACE inhibitors; Digoxin; Calcium channel blocker; Antiarrhythmic agents; hypoglycemic drugs; Opioids; CNS depressants; tricyclic antidepressants; anti-cholinergic phenothiazines; CNS stimulant.	13
6	Drug of Abuse: Opioids; Cocaine; phencyclidine; marijuana; Lysergic acid.	4
7	Chemical and Environmental Toxins: Hydrocarbones; Household toxins; Antiseptic; Disinfectants; Camphor; moth repellents.	3
8	Botanicals and plants-derived toxins: Herbal preparation; Toxic plants; Poisonous mushrooms.	4

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of **pharmaceutics**

Title of the course: **Therapeutic Drug Monitoring**

Level: **4th Class 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 2 hours**

Reference Text:

1-Applied biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics, Shargel and Yu. Latest edition

2-Applied Clinical Pharmacokinetics.by Larry A. Bauer. Latest edition

Objectives: The course deals with the physical and chemical properties of drug substance, dosage form and the biological effectiveness of the drug or drug product upon administration, including drug availability in the human or animal body from a given dosage form. The pharmacokinetic part of the course deals with the time-course of the drug in the biological system, and quantification of drug concentration pattern in normal subjects and in certain disease states, in addition to therapeutic drug monitoring

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction to Biopharmaceutics and Pharmacokinetics	2
2	Biopharmaceutic Considerations in Drug Product Design	3
3	Physiologic Factors Related to Drug Absorption	2
4	Bioavailability and Bioequivalence	2
5	One-Compartment Open Model: Intravenous Bolus Administration	2
6	Multicompartment Models: Intravenous Bolus Administration	2
7	Intravenous Infusion	2
8	Drug Elimination and Clearance	2
9	Pharmacokinetics of Oral Absorption	2
10	Multiple-Dosage Regimens	2
11	Nonlinear Pharmacokinetics	2
12	Hepatic Elimination of Drugs	2
13	Clinical Pharmacokinetic Equations and Calculations	2
14	Drug Dosing in Special Populations	2
15	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Aminoglycoside Antibiotics	2
16	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Vancomycin	2
17	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Digoxin	2
18	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Lidocaine	2
19	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Phenytoin	2
20	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Cyclosporine	2
21	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Lithium	2
22	Therapeutic drug monitoring; Theophylline	2

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Pharmacotherapy II**

Level: **4th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 3 hours.**

Reference Text:

1- Joseph T. DiPiro, Robert L. Pharmacotherapy: A Pathophysiologic Approach. Latest edition.

2- Mary Anne koda-kimble (ed.), Applied Therapeutics: The clinical use of drugs. Latest edition.

3- Marie A. Chisholm-Burns .Pharmacotherapy Principles & Practice. Latest edition.

Objective:

The course provides students with the basic knowledge about pathophysiology, symptoms and aims of treatment. In addition to the basic knowledge on the drug's use, kinetics drug interactions, dose calculations, side effects, treatment algorithms and patient awareness. The diseases of the following topics will be covered: Renal Disorders, Diseases of Infectious Origin, and Bone and Joint Disorders

No	Lecture title	hours
1.	Interpretation of Lab. data.	2
2.	Acute coronary syndrome.	2
3.	Arrhythmias	2
4.	Thrombosis	2
5.	Dyslipidemia	2
6.	Stroke	2
7.	Shock	2
8.	Liver cirrhosis	2
9.	Viral hepatitis	1

10.	Inflammatory bowel diseases	2
11.	Acute kidney injury	1
12.	Chronic kidney disease	2
13.	Hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis	1
14.	Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE)	1
15.	Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH)	1
16.	Acid – base disorders	2
17.	Disorders of fluid and electrolytes	2
18.	Urinary incontinence and pediatric enuresis	1
19.	Epilepsy and status epilepticus	2
20.	Multiple sclerosis	1
21.	Parkinson's disease	2
22.	Pain management	2
23.	Headache disorders	2
24.	Parenteral nutrition	2
25.	Enteral nutrition	2
26.	Pharmacovigilance	2

College of Pharmacy
Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Case study in therapeutics II**

Level: **4th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours /week : Theory 3

Reference:

1-Soraya Dhillon. pharmacy case studies. Latest edition.

2- Linda J Dodds. Drugs in Use Clinical case studies for pharmacists. Latest edition.

3-Mary Anne koda-kimble (ed.), Applied Therapeutics: The clinical use of drugs. Latest edition.

4-David M. Angaran, Karen L. Whalen. Medication therapy management : a comprehensive approach. Latest edition.

Objective:

During this course, the students will use clinical cases to develop the students' ability to assess patients conditions, determine reasonable treatment alternatives, select appropriate therapy and monitoring parameters, and to justify those choices by utilizing knowledge & skills acquired in therapeutics.

No	Lecture title	Hours
1.	Case studies about Acute coronary syndrome.	3
2.	Case studies about Arrhythmias	3
3.	Case studies about Thrombosis	3
4.	Case studies about Dyslipidemia	3
5.	Case studies about Stroke	2
6.	Case studies about Epilepsy and status epilepticus	2
7.	Case studies about Multiple sclerosis	2
8.	Case studies about Parkinson's disease	2
9.	Case studies about Headache disorders	2
10.	Case studies about Acute kidney injury	2
11.	Case studies about Chronic kidney disease	3
12.	Case studies about Liver cirrhosis	3

13.	Case studies about Viral hepatitis	2
14.	Case studies about Inflammatory bowel diseases	3
15.	Case studies about Parenteral nutrition	2
16.	Case studies about Enteral nutrition	1
17.	Case studies about Acid – base disorders	2
18.	Case studies about Disorders of fluid and electrolytes	2
19.	Case studies about Benign prostatic hyperplasia	1
20.	Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs)	2

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **First Aid and Emergency Medicine**

Level: **4th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 1 hour.**

Reference:

1- Karren, K., & et al.) First Aid For Colleges And Universities. American Heart Association. Latest edition.

Objective:

The course covers general principles and techniques of first aid at premedical stage in case of life-threatening situations. Introduction to first aid and emergency medicine for all ages and systems of the body.

No	title	hours
1	Introduction to the course (Definition of first aid, Goals of first aid training, Role and responsibilities of first aid provider, Legal aspect of first aid)	1

2	First aid basics [First aid kit, Types of emergency transport, General first aid procedure, Victim and rescuer safety, Primary and secondary assessment (Finding the problem)].	2
3	Basic life support (BLS) [Adult chain of survival, Adult, child, and infant CPR , Airway obstruction (adult, child and infant)]	2
4	Medical emergencies (Breathing problems, Bad allergic reactions, Heart attack, Fainting, Diabetes and low blood sugar, Stroke, Seizures, Shock).	2
5	Injury emergencies (Bleeding and wounds, Head, neck, and spine injury (spinal care and lifting), Broken bones and sprains, Burns and electrocution, Eye and ear injuries, Chest and pelvic injuries)	3
6	Environmental emergencies[Bites and stings (Snake bites; Insect, Bee and Spider bites), Temperature related emergencies, Poison emergencies (Specific toxins: Acids, Alkalis, Hydrocarbons, Methanol, Cyanide, Salicylates, Acetaminophen);Food poisoning]	3
7	Collective practice I	1
8	Collective practice II	1

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College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Evidence Based Practice& Scientific Writing**

Level: **4th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 2 hours.**

ReferenceText:

1-Patrick J. Bryant and Heather A. Pace. Pharmacist's Guide to Evidence-Based Medicine for Clinical Decision Making. Latest edition.

2-Phil Wiffen. Evidence-based Pharmacy. Radcliffe Medical Press.Latest edition.

3-The complete guide to medical writing. Edited by Mark C Stuart. Pharmaceutical press. Latest edition.

4-Relevant original and review articles from scientific journals.

Objective:

We aim to enable students to identify, obtain, evaluate and utilize published medical literature to be used in patient care, research projects and lifelong learning. In addition to providing students with essential skills and basic principles of medical writing.

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction on evidence based medicine	2
2	Medical literature and the main searching engine (google scholar, pubmed, medline..).	2
3	Overview of Study design and strength of evidence	3
4	Examples on different types of observational studies	2
5	Examples on different types of clinical trials.	2
6	Review of basic statistics (hypothesis, terms like confidence interval, mean, frequency,...)	2
7	Main statistical tests in medical research (T test, chi square, correlations, regression analysis)	3
8	Introduction to SPSS and other statistics computer programs	2
9	Critical appraisal for published article (Sources of bias, Hierarchy of evidence, Internal and external beliefs)	3
10	Applicability and strength of evidence.	1
11	Communicating evidence to patients	2
12	Principles and skills of writing research proposal and projects, medical case report, conference poster, examination and assessment paper, presentation materials, and styles of reference writing	4
13	Designing and developing questionnaires	2

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Pharm D Seminar**

Level: **4th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 2 hour.**

Reference:

1-Relevant original and review articles from scientific journals.

Objective:

This course will prepare students for presentation in journal club as well as for other assigned topics from didactics, to train the students for effective scientific presentation and scientific communication through response to the questions.

The use of multimedia, slides, overheads, handouts and other visual aids as well as methods of answering questions from the audience will also be discussed in this course.

No	title	hours
1	Introduction [(Introduction to critical Steps in the selection of the research article. In addition to the presentation skills (including presentation programs and criteria for the effective presentation)].	3
2	Presentation of seminars [For the oral presentation, every student has to select a relevant topic in pharmacy practice (from previously published articles) and present it to cover the scope of topic followed by discussion and answering the questions]. Emphasis will be on the evaluation of drug literature	12

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College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: Introductory hospital Pharmacy Practice Experience **II**

Level: **5th Class, 1st Semester**

Credit hours: **Laboratory 4 : [for 15 weeks, 120 hours (8 hours/week over 2 training days)].**

Reference Text:

Manuals prepared by the Clinical Pharmacy Department.

Objective:

The course is designed to provide initial experience of institutional pharmacy practice as well as essential clinical pharmacy skills in preparation for their experiential rotations in hospitals and clinics with emphasis on dealing with patients, medical charts, laboratory information, and clinical monitoring. It is an early practice experience component that involves a patient workup under the mentorship of preceptors. The following topics will be covered:

Paediatrics, Nephrology, Rheumatology and surgery.

No	Rotation name	weeks	Hours
1	Paediatrics	6	48
2	Surgery	4	32
3	Rheumatology	3	24
4	Nephrology	2	16

Summer training II (Community pharmacy practice)